

MAHALLA TUSHUNCHASINING VUJUDGA KELISHI HAQIDA

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Annotatsiya. Mahalla institutining rivojlanish tarixi bir necha bosqichlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Mahalla ijtimoiy tuzilma sifatida qadim zamonlardan buyon mamlakatimizda ma'rifat markazi, fuqarolarning o'zini-o'zi boshqarish tizimining samarali shakli bo'lib kelgan. Mahalla - Sharq tamadduni, xususan, Markaziy osiyo xalqlari turmush tarzi, tafakkuri va qadriyatlarini o'zida aks ettirgan jamiyat hayotini tashkil etadigan an'anaviy ijtimoiy institut. "Mahalla" so'zi arab tilida tarjima qilinganda "turar-joy", "qo'nalg'a", "shaharning qismi" degan ma'nolarni anglatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: mahalla, jamoa, urf-odatlar, hashar, oila, "turar-joy", "qo'nalg'a", "shaharning qismi".

ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD

Abstract. The development history of the neighborhood institution includes several stages. The neighborhood as a social structure has been a center of enlightenment in our country since ancient times, an effective form of the self-management system of citizens. Mahalla is a traditional social institution that organizes the life of society, reflecting the lifestyle, thinking and values of Eastern civilization, in particular, the peoples of Central Asia. The word "Mahalla" in Arabic means "residence", "neighbourhood", "part of the city".

Key words: neighborhood, community, traditions, hashar, family, "residence", "house", "part of the city".

О ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИИ ПОНЯТИЯ СОСЕДСТВА

Аннотация. История развития учреждения микрорайона включает в себя несколько этапов. Район как социальная структура издавна является центром просвещения в нашей стране, эффективной формой системы самоуправления граждан. Махалля – традиционный социальный институт, организующий жизнь общества, отражающий образ жизни, мышление и ценности восточной цивилизации, в частности, народов Центральной Азии. Слово «Махалля» в переводе с арабского означает «резиденция», «район», «часть города».

Ключевые слова: квартал, община, традиции, хашар, семья, «резиденция», «дом», «часть города».

Qadimda mahalla nafaqat ijtimoiy tuzilma, balki ma'muriy-hududiy tuzilma sifatida ham e'tirof etilgan. Qadimgi davr arxeologik manbalarining guvohlik berishicha, bronza davri manzilgohi hisoblangan Sopollitepada sakkizta patriarxal oila istiqomat qilgan, ularni qarindoshlik rishlarigina emas, jamoadagi xo'jalik manfaatlari ham uyushtirgan. Vaqt o'tgani sayin ular safiga yuzdan ortiq oilalar kelib qo'shilgan. Qarindoshlardan tashkil topgan oilalar jamoasini, oqsoqollar boshqarib kelganlar¹. Oqsoqollar saylov yo'li bilan jamoa tomonidan

¹ Бўриев о., Саидов Б. Махалла – миллий тарихий институт. – Тошкент: Янги нашр, - Б.13

tayinlangan. Jamoa hayotiga oid muhim masalalar oqsoqol boshchilik qiladigan “Oqsoqollar kengashi”da qabul qilingan.

Qadimgi Dovon davlatida ham oqsoqollar kengashi davlat hayotida muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan. Yuqoridagilardan ham koʻrinib turibdiki, mahalla instituti ildizlari qadimga borib taqaladi.

Bu tuzilma jamiyat hayotida, ijtimoiy munosabatlarda muhim rol oʻynab kelgan. Insonlarning bir-biriga boʻlgan ehtiyoji ularni jamoa birlashib yashashiga sabab boʻgan. Abu Nasr Farobiy “Fozil shahar aholisi haqida mulohazalar” asarida odamlar sonining koʻpayishi sababli inson jamoalariga boʻlgan ehtiyoj gʻoyasini ochib beradi. “Har bir inson tabiiy ravishda shu tarzda joylashtirilgan, yashash va obodonlashtirishga intilish uchun unga koʻp narsalar kerak, ammo u yolgʻiz oʻzi ularni oʻzlashtira olmaydi, bunga erishishi uchun insoniyat hamjamiyatiga ehtiyoj paydo boʻladi. Jamiyat aʼzolarining birgalikdagi faoliyati ularga oʻsha narsalarga erishish va oʻzlashtirish imkoniyatini beradi”. Qomusiy olim Abu Ali ibn Sino “Uy-roʻzgʻor toʻgrisida” nomli risolasida “Insonlarning bir-birlarining ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun ularga umumiy intilish va maqsadlar kerak” – deya, taʼkidlaydi².

Ulugʻ mutafakkir Nosir Xisrav oʻzining 1043-1052 yillarda Yaqin Sharq mamlakatlariga qilgan sayohati davomida yozgan “Safarnoma” asarida “Qohira shahri 10 ta mahallotdan iborat”- deya taʼkidlaydi. U turli mintaqalarda mahallot (joy), guzar, jamoa, elat, elod nomlarda atalib kelingan. Adabiyotlarda mahallalarning koʻp ming yillik tarixga ega ekanligi haqida maʼlumotlar uchraydi. Masalan, Narshaxiy oʻzining „Buxoro tarixi“ asarida Buxoroda bundan 1100-yil ilgari bir qancha mahallalar boʻlganini qayd etib oʻtgan³. Alisher Navoiy oʻzining „Hayrat ul-abror“ asarida mahallani “mahalla shahar ichidagi shaharcha“dir-deb taʼriflaydi, Hirot shahri yuz shaharcha ahamiyatiga ega boʻlgan mahallalardan tashkil topganini aytib oʻtadi⁴. Mahallalar, ayniqsa, Amir Temur davrida ravnaq topgan. Bu davrda mahallalar fuqarolarning kasbkori asosida shakllangan va shunga qarab nomlangan. Masalan, zargarlik, misgarlik, koʻnchilik, pichoqchilik, qoshiqchilik, temirchi, egarchi, taqachi va h.k. Mahmud Qoshgʻariyning “Devon-u lugʻati-turk” asarida savdo va hunarmandchilik kvartallarini bildiruvchi ibora sifatida “mahalla” soʻzi qoʻllanilgan. Mahalla qadimda mahalliy hokimiyatning oʻziga xos bir shakli, koʻrinishi tarzida faoliyat koʻrsatgan. Uni boshqarish jamoatchilik asosida olib borilib, oʻzining yozilmagan ichki tartib-qoidalariga ega boʻlib, u hamma uchun birdek qonuniy hisoblangan.

Mahalla xalqimizning turmush tarzi, ruhiy - maʼnaviy ehtiyoji, mafkurasi, tafakkuri, insonlarning oʻzaro qoʻshnichilik aloqalari, oilaviy munosabatlarni shakllantiruvchi maʼnaviy-maʼrifiy maskan, kengash, maslahat, hashar kabi milliy udumlar xalq sayllari, bayramlar uyushtiriladigan qoʻni-qoʻshnichilik, quda-andachilik kabi masalalar hal etiladigan serqirra ijtimoiy tuzilma hisoblandi. Xalqimiz dunyoqarashi, feʼl-atvori, milliy mentaliteti haqida gap ketganda shaxsning ijtimoiylashuvida jamoatchilikning oʻrni alohida ahamiyat kasb etishini taʼkidlash zarur. Sharqlik inson oʻz hayotini jamoatchilikning tajribasi, axloqiy meʼyorlari va moddiy koʻmagisiz tasavvur etmaydi.

² Abu Ali ibn Sino. Tib konunlari.- Toshkent,1992.-B.89

³ Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Jaфар an-Narshaxiy. Buxoro tarixi.-Toshkent,1993.-B. 30-45

⁴ Alisher Navoiy. Xayratul abror.- Toshkent,1999. - B.89

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